

Evidence-Based Toxicology Manuscript Assessment Report

TEBT-2023-0002: Protocol for designing INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies

First round of peer review | 26 04 2023

Note about EBT's manuscript assessment process: The EBT protocol assessment process evaluates a submitted protocol for demonstrating that, if followed, enough scientific work would be done that the relevant community would consider the anticipated study to be a unit of contribution to the scientific literature. We define a unit of contribution as any useful, valid piece of research.

The first stage of assessment is Editorial Triage, where the Handling Editor assesses a protocol for compliance with EBT's minimum requirements for submissions. Protocols judged as meeting EBT's minimum requirements go to peer-review, where three or four reviewers provide comments about how the protocol could or should be modified, to make the planned study the best contribution to the literature that it can realistically be. These comments are aggregated by the Handling Editor into an Assessment Report (this document).

The authors, reviewers, and Handling Editor then discuss the Assessment Report and attempt to come to consensus on the most appropriate way to modify the protocol, through a combination of one or more of planning additional experimental work, modifying the data analysis plan, and revising how the research is described. If necessary, a revised protocol is re-reviewed, further discussions held, and changes made, until the Handling Editor, authors, and peer-reviewers are satisfied that enough work has been done for the protocol to count as an Accepted Contribution to the literature. At this point the version of record of the protocol is formally published in the journal.

The structure of this assessment report is derived from the reviewer and author guidelines for Registered Reports (Chambers et al. 2023, <https://osf.io/pukzy>).

Protocol title	Protocol for designing INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7633627
Submission Type	study protocol
Report authors	Olwenn V Martin, EBT journal Handling editor Catherine Gibbons, USEPA Kaitlyn Hair, CAMARADES, University of Edinburgh Anonymous reviewers: 1
Recommendation	Minor mostly editorial revisions: Reviewers did not find any issues that would have a material impact on findings of the research but highlighted several other issues that would improve accessibility and understanding if addressed.
Explanation	Reviewers found that the described protocol was rigorous and did address the lack of authoritative tools to evaluate the internal validity of in vitro methods. Authors should edit the introduction to clarify the wider context (future increased regulatory reliance on NAMs, PARC including related initiatives) and scope of the proposed work (in vitro methods vs NAMs). They should also attempt to describe intended user group in more detail.

The analysis pipeline is sound overall but would be improved if the rationale for the selection of study participants for the successive studies was provided. Further details should be provided, particularly for studies 1 and 3, to further improve the transparency and reproducibility of the methods. Specifically, the value of using examples was highlighted by all reviewers. Most suggested changes are editorial in nature and represent requests for clarification. These changes are feasible and likely to be acceptable to the authors. The sourcing of examples may require significant additional work, this is more likely to be resisted by the authors but is considered feasible.

Summary of reviewer comments

[Insert here a brief summary of protocol for an external for reader of this report: what is it trying to achieve, what is its overall method, etc. If relevant, include a brief summary of how the protocol has been changed in response to reviewer comments.]

This protocol proposes to address the current lack of consensus tools for evaluating the internal validity of in vitro studies. It describes three of the four studies that will be performed to create the release version of such a tool, INVITES-IN. The first study combines an evaluation of existing assessment tools with focus group discussions to identify how characteristics of the design or conduct of an in vitro study can affect its internal validity. The second study will use a modified Delphi methodology reach group agreement on internal validity domains and items of importance for in vitro studies. In the third study, the draft version of INVITES-IN will be created. User testing, validation of the tool, and collection of users' experience will consist the fourth study and will be described in a separate protocol.

Seriousness of issues identified with planned methods	Reviewers did not identify any issues that would have a material impact on the study findings.
Potential additional work to overcome issues	Other issues identified by reviewers are editorial in nature, to improve clarity of scope, understanding and accessibility.
Acceptability of characterising limitations instead of planning additional work	It should be possible for authors to readily address reviewers' comments.

Structured assessment

1. Are the research questions important?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
---	---	--	--	---

Comments: Reviewers found that the described protocol was rigorous, did address the lack of authoritative tools to evaluate the internal validity of in vitro methods, and that the resulting tool would be of interest to stakeholders in regulatory toxicology and the evidence synthesis community.

Suggestions for addressing the comments: None

2. Are the proposed hypotheses logical, rational, and/or plausible?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
---	---	--	---	--

Comments: The rationale for the approach could be brought into sharper focus by offering further details and clarifications on the wider context for the project (PARC) and scope of the proposed work (in vitro vs NAMS).

Reviewer 1:

- 1.1. Section 1.1 Objective: “we intend that the tool be applicable (potentially with modification) to other in vitro designs or other NAMS such as organ-on-a-chip, in ovo, fish embryos, ex vivo, in chemico, etc., and chemical mixture studies”. Are these in vitro systems included in the protocol development or not? Please clarify.
- 1.2. I would further recommend to describe the target group of tool users. What is their expected expertise? And what is the intended duration required for evaluating one study? This would certainly have an impact on the design of the tool.

Reviewer 2:

- 2.1. This work is part of a larger project – PARC. Could you briefly place this work in context and explain why the development of this tool a first step i.e. the focus on in vitro studies and on internal validity? Is other work ongoing to develop the other parts of the framework laid out in the Introduction?
- 2.2. Add some context around your decision to focus primarily on cell culture models – I’m assuming this is related to greater translatability and/or use in recent years?

Reviewer 3:

- 3.1. Pages 3-4, lines 71-127: The introduction starts and ends with a statement that this tool is for the evaluation of the internal validity of in vitro studies, but the bulk of the text emphasizes the development of this tool for NAMS. It might make more sense to invert the emphasis and include more discussion focused on the importance of developing a tool for evaluating in vitro studies, provided within the context of the future needs related to increased reliance on NAMS.
- 3.2. Page 2, lines 55-57, and page 4, lines 116-118: I would avoid using imprecise terms like “obviously authoritative” here and instead reframe as a prior lack of consensus on developing a tool with the application of rigorous methods, which is what the following sentence describes.
- 3.3. Pages 3-4, lines 89-99: This framework would be more useful if further context is provided. It perhaps wasn’t deemed necessary to describe the other steps in this protocol, but it would still be helpful to either provide more detail here or refer to another broad research plan that describes the plans for addressing each principle in as rigorous a way as has been done in this protocol for #2. In particular, #1 will be of interest, since we have found it to be impractical to identify and define inclusion criteria a priori for what evidence will be the most relevant to answering a regulatory toxicology-based research question when considering as broad and diverse an evidence base as NAMS.

Suggestions for addressing the comments: Authors should edit the introduction to clarify the wider context (future increased regulatory reliance on NAMS, PARC including related initiatives) and rationale for the specific focus on cell-based (in vitro) bioassays. They should also attempt to describe intended user group in more detail. These changes are clarifications and such changes are likely feasible and acceptable to the authors.

3. Is the methodology and analysis pipeline sound (and, if appropriate, statistically powered)?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
---	---	--	---	--

Comments: The analysis pipeline is sound overall but would be improved if the rationale for the selection of study participants for the successive studies was provided.

Reviewer 2:

- 2.1. Could you explain your rationale for the different sets of study participants required for studies 1 & 3 versus 2?
- 2.2. Will focus group and workshop participants be offered co-authorship or will this be limited to Delphi round participants?

Suggestions for addressing the comments: Authors should provide the further information required by reviewer 2. These changes represent clarifications and such changes are likely feasible and acceptable to the authors.

4. Are the methods detailed and clear enough to permit replication of the experimental procedures and analysis pipeline?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
---	---	--	---	--

Comments: The transparency and reproducibility of the methods would be improved if further details were provided, particularly for studies 1 and 3. Specifically, the value of using examples was highlighted by all reviewers.

Reviewer 1:

- 1.1. Section 2.1 Study design: I would have expected that the technical implementation (which platform: online tool?, how provided to the users?) would also be part of the study design and would merit some detail.
- 1.2. Section 2.22 Method: Although the protocol needs to be clear and straight (which it is), it would improve the readability if some aspects of in vitro studies would be addressed at least in exemplary form. For example, it does not become clear to me in which bias domain an in vitro test would fall which does not have suitable metabolic capacity for the specific research question it is used for. On the other hand it remains obscure to me what an attrition bias would be in case of in vitro tests. Examples for each domain would be helpful.

Reviewer 2:

- 2.1. I am still unclear on how the focus groups will operate (Study 1). How will the list of identified bias domains/ items from the literature SRs interact with the SEVCO domains? Will you have preselected example items to discuss under each domain?
- 2.2. In study 1, the third question on “Should INVITES-IN ask users to judge risk of bias directly under a set of organising...?” may be particularly challenging for those without SR experience. Could this be altered or perhaps integrated later as part of the Delphi or the workshops?
- 2.3. The detail on workshop structure and what you will ask participants in Study 3 is lacking (compared to the description of the other studies).
- 2.4. Why is a balanced regional distribution not required for Study 3? (Table 1)
- 2.5. In study 3, have you considered sourcing examples (i.e. text from a paper reporting a specific item) to place alongside the signalling questions and guidance documentation? In my experience, examples aid understanding and can be especially helpful for those with less critical appraisal experience.

Reviewer 3:

- 3.1. Table 2, last row (study 1, p12): “Early study termination bias” seems oddly specific in this more general list of bias domains and it isn’t immediately clear how this is broadly relevant to in vitro assays. I recommend making this an “other” domain to cover bias due to problems not covered elsewhere, including this one, as is used in the OHAT Handbook (2019).

Suggestions for addressing the comments: Most suggested changes are editorial in nature and represent requests for clarification. These changes are feasible and likely to be acceptable to the authors. The sourcing of examples may require significant additional work, this is more likely to be resisted by the authors but is considered feasible.

5. Have the authors specified sufficient outcome-neutral tests for ensuring the results obtained can test the stated hypotheses?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
---	---	--	--	--

Comments: Not applicable – testing the stated hypotheses will form part of a fourth study to be described in a separate protocol.

Suggestions for addressing the comments: None

Other comments

Reviewer 1:

- 1.1. Abstract: the first part of the abstract is an introduction to the topic, which, should not be part of the abstract. The abstract should describe the work which led to this manuscript, i.e. preparing the protocol.
- 1.2. Section 1 and 2.1 start with text followed by subheadings. If subheadings are used all text should be under such subheadings.
- 1.3. Whaley et al., in preparation: It is not in the reference list (no title, no journal, no co-authors). If there is only an intention to write such a systematic review I would rather recommend to mention it in the discussion, if considered necessary.
- 1.4. “; we are not aware of a single published tool for the assessment of the internal validity of in vitro studies that follows all the steps we have outlined in our protocol” If the authors make such claims they should cite the tools they have in mind (at least the most relevant ones) and should exemplify the shortcomings.

Reviewer 2:

- 2.1. Lines 83-85 (Introduction) repeat the definition of NAMS described previously. Rephrase or remove to avoid repetition.

Handling editor:

- Please check table numbering